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PHYSICAL EXERCISE TECHNIQUES

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Abstract: *This article provides an overview of exercise theory based on pedagogical tasks and provides feedback on the teacher's options for choosing the most effective exercise.*

Key words: *Physical training, exercise, sports equipment, technical training, athletes.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье представлен обзор теории упражнений на основе педагогических задач и дана обратная связь о возможностях учителя по выбору наиболее эффективного упражнения.*

Ключевые слова: *Физическая культура, упражнения, спортивный инвентарь, техническая подготовка, спортсмены.*

As far as we know, physical education is a form of education based on the state program. Sports are carried out through special trainings and competitions based on the requirements and criteria of the classification programs. The content of physical education classes, first of all, includes parts (elements) of various exercises, games and sports. This means that physical education classes are conducted according to specific procedures and without any restrictions.

The word technique means mastery. Exercise is the process by which an athlete performs specific actions in practice to achieve a high level of skill and results in a particular type. Exercise includes physical, technical, tactical, spiritual, and volitional training. Sports technique is a method of solving movement tasks characterized by high efficiency.

Athletes' technical training is characterized by the level of mastery of the system of movements by the athlete, which ensures high sports results. Athletes' technical training is aimed at solving a number of complex tasks - improving the efficiency of maximum voltage, saving working voltage, increasing the speed and accuracy of movement in the changing conditions of competitive activities. Improving sports technique takes many years of preparation. Technical mastery means perfect mastery of the most intelligent movement techniques in the conditions of intense sports competitions. There are three stages in improving technical skills.

1. Research.
2. Stabilization
3. Improve adaptability.

Technical readiness control is important for every coach to monitor and analyze training process management loads. Managing a training process involves three steps.

1. Collect information about the site of observation and the external environment in which the object is formed.
2. Analyze the data obtained.
3. Decision making and planning.

Modern coaches today need to regularly analyze the level of training load and compare it with the performance of the competition.

Knowledge of exercise theory allows the teacher to choose the most effective exercise based on the following pedagogical tasks. The concept of exercise is defined as the relationship between a person's movements and motor activities. Movement is a motor function of the body that changes the state of the body and its parts. Free movement, not innate movement, is important for physical education, and it is a movement that depends on the will of man. As IP Pavlov puts it, "Movement from the cerebral cortex: each movement is characterized by 3 signs:

- It is a function of the mind.
 - Acquired as a result of the activities of the life process in conjunction with the learning process.
 - Movement training increases students' ability to submit to their will.
- a) Movement activity is a means to perform a specific movement task (overcoming obstacles, jumping long or high, choosing the right equipment, accurately hitting the target, and so on and so forth).
 - b) Motion activity technique is the most optimal way to perform this movement activity.
 - c) In sports, the use of sports techniques is the optimal way to perform these sports movements (exercises). Unlike the meaning of everyday (home) equipment, sports equipment has its own characteristics.

g) Individual technique is a model technique that is adapted to the characteristics of the athlete's physical development and his psychomotor qualities.

The basics of exercise biotechnology include movement techniques: bending, straightening, turning, throwing, and other specific movements. In complex motion techniques, the technical basis and technical details differ from each other.

The basis of the technique is the general contour of the entire locomotor system, that is, running, landing, flying and landing while performing the long jump exercise.

REFERENCES

1. Kerimov F.A. "Sport sohasidagi ilmiy tadqiqotlar" T., 2003 y.
2. Kerimov. F.T. "Sport kurash nazariyasi va usuliyati" T., 2005 y.
3. Raximov M.M. "Sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va uslubiyati asoslari" T., 2006 y.
4. Salomov R.S. "Sport mashg'ulotining nazariy asoslari" T.,2005 y.
5. Goncharova O.V. "Yosh sportchilarning jismoniy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish" T., 2005 y.
6. Xasanov, Anvar. (2017). Физическая культура и спорт как важный аспект в формировании личности. Форум молодых ученых. 5. 425-428.
7. Xasanov, Anvar. (2017). Физическая культура-надежда нации. Форум молодых ученых. 5. 591.
8. Xasanov, Anvar & Mamanazarova, A. (2022). Website: www.sjird.journalspark.org WRESTLING PREPARATION PROCESS IN SPORTS SCHOOLS. SPECTRUM Journal of Gender and Children Studies. 19. 174.
9. Yakhshilikov, Sanjar. (2023). UNAVOIDABLE CLASHES: EXPLORING THE IMPLICATIONS OF A CHINA-RUSSIA ALLIANCE ON GLOBAL GEOPOLITICS. Austral Brazilian Journal of Strategy & International Relations. 12. 198-209. 10.22456/2238-6912.131366.
10. Nurmatov, Eldor. (2023). Maqola Jurnal chet el.
11. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). METHODS OF FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE FOR CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY.
12. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). РОЛЬ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МОТИВАЦИИ.
13. Nurmatov, Eldor. (2023). Maqola Jurnal chet el.
14. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). РОЛЬ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МОТИВАЦИИ.
15. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). ORGANIZING TOURIST TRIPS WITH

STUDENTS Anvar Toxirovich Hasanov JDPU. "Physical culture" faculty. Journal of Physical Education.

16. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). DUTIES OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS ON THE FIELD Anvar Takhirovich Hasanov JDPU. "Physical culture" faculty.

17. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). Forming a conscious attitude of adolescents towards their health. 10.13140/RG.2.2.25438.41289.

18. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). РОЛЬ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ МОТИВАЦИИ.

19. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS Anvar Takhirovich Hasanov JDPU. "Physical culture" faculty.

20. Atamurodov, Shodiyor. (2023). ТУРИСТИК САЁХАТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ.

21. Nomozov, Abdurashid. (2023). Sogʻlom turmush tarziga sportning ahamiyati hamda oʻrni qanchalik muhimligini taʼsir etuvchi omillari..

22. Buriboyev, Alisher. (2023). Komil inson tarbiyasida jismoniy madaniyatning oʻrni.

23. Yakhshilikov, S. (2023). UNAVOIDABLE CLASHES: EXPLORING THE IMPLICATIONS OF A CHINA-RUSSIA ALLIANCE ON GLOBAL GEOPOLITICS. AUSTRAL: Brazilian Journal of Strategy & International Relations, 12(23). <https://doi.org/10.22456/2238-6912.131366>

24. Xasanov, Anvar. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS 'INTEREST IN SUBJECTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. 5.2. 346-349.